

**IMPACT OF DAIRY FARMING ON EDUCATIONAL STATUS IN
KOLHAPUR DISTRICT: A CASE STUDY**

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Abstract

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy. According to the census of India, 69% of population is still engaged in agriculture sector. About 70% of Indian export depends upon agriculture products; includes dairy products. Kolhapur district is known for its Krishna valley stock for more than hundred years and has a long tradition for dairy farming and it impacts on overall development of the district. The present paper intends to focus on the impact dairy farming on educational status in the district. The literacy level measured at Tehsils and at case study village level which was surveyed in Feb. 2011. In 2001 census, the average literacy of the district was 72.59 per cent and in 2011 it was 77.82 per cent, the absolute increase was 5.23 per cent. The average female literacy rate was 60.47% & male was 84.72% and gap was 24.25 % in 2001. As per 2011 census it was 69.22 % female average literacy rate and while males were 86.31 % and the gap was 17.09 % means slightly decreased by 7.16 %. At the case study villages level the total average was 73.47 % and male average was 82.93% and 63.51 % of female average. The total gap average was 19.44 %, as per the field in feb.2011. The study also focuses on the educational attainment of the children's in the case study villages.

Key words: Agriculture, Dairy farming, dairy products, literacy level, educational attainment

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy, according to the census of India, 69% of population is engaged in agriculture. The role of agriculture in the field of international trade is very much important to understand the economic development. About 70% of Indian export depends upon agriculture products (Kumar, L. S. S., 1963). Eradication of rural poverty and income inequality is one of the principal objectives of agricultural development policy in our country. Subsidiary occupation is to be adapted to tackle the problem of poverty and inequality. Agriculture and dairying is the largest source of income and employment for the rural people.

Maharashtra is one of the major state in India, and it is the third largest state in area and population. Maharashtra enjoys the place of pride in the national pursuit of milk as "White Revolution". Studies have shown that the milk co-operative has the potentialities of going a long way in improving the economic and social handicaps of the farmer with the view. Governments of Maharashtra has paid special attention and made financial provisions such as grants, subsidies and share capital for the milk co-operatives. Because of such efforts, the number of primary milk co-operatives and union in the state has gone up.

Kolhapur district comprising the valleys of Warana, Panchganga and their tributaries has been developed the fertile and producing soil. The transitional geographical location of the district between the Konkan costal low land to the west ocean, plateau to the east, presents a variety in the geographical environment. (Sarang, S.B.1982). Development of agro based industry like, sugar industry in the co-operative sector has helped the dairy farming to the greater extent through availability of capital for progressive investment. There is market increases in the land under food crops. Which is responsible for changing the agriculture pattern and has influenced the dairy farming to a considerable extent? Kolhapur district is known for its Krishna valley stock for more than hundred years and has a long tradition for dairy farming. There is very limited scope for further increase in the

land under crops as the western and southern parts of the Kolhapur district are the hilly ranged. Kolhapur has well developed transportation and communication facilities, therefore the agriculture and agro base industries are developed in the district. Shri Hanuman Co-operative Dudh Utpadak Sangh Yalgud is well established unit for the dairy farming and development in the catchments area of Yalgud, Randewadi, Tal. Hatkangale, of Kolhapur district, and Mangur Tal. Chikkodi dist Belgaum and surrounding area, as it fulfils many physical and cultural requirements for the establishment and growth of dairying in the Kolhapur district. The dairy farming in the district is functioning in the co-operative sector and the people of the district possess a keen sense of co-operative in every walk of life which is developed as a result of development of co-operative industries, farming and credit societies during last 50 years.

STUDY AREA

For the project work, the Kolhapur district is selected as district unit and for case study, the villages from catchments area of Shri Hanuman co-op. Dudh Utpadak Sangh Ltd. Yalgud, to look in to the Dairy Farming and Development. The geographical position of district in the state of Maharashtra is one of the south-western parts of Deccan Plateau, the district which is known as most fertile and well drained district of the state.

From the location point of view, the district is extent between from 73°00' to 74°00' east longitude and 15°6' to 17°3' north latitude. The Kolhapur district has an area of 7685 Sq/Km with the population of 3876001 (2011). The Kolhapur district is bounded by Belgaum district (Karnataka state) in southern the Sahyadri lanes in the west, the Warna River in the north, and the river Krishna and some part of Belgaum district of Karnataka state in the east. The average height of the district is about 390 to 600m. For this present study, we have chosen the agriculturally well grown area from Kolhapur district. This study carried out in Yalgud, Randewadi, and Mangur villages, these villages are located in Kolhapur, and Belgaum districts.

OBJECTIVES:

The objective of the present study is to examine the impact of dairy farming on Educational status in Kolhapur district.

DATA BASE AND METHODOLOGY:

In order to meet this objective, the study is mainly based on primary data as well as secondary sources of data. The primary data, which have been collected by conducting by the intensive field work in the selected village's viz. Randewadi, Mangur, and Yalgud. Near about 60 houses were surveyed out of these three. It has helped us to get information about dairy farming and development in villages. The data was collected with help of household schedule which were pre-tested. Information was collected with the help of interviews with the individual milk producers in the selected villages, chairman secretaries and servants of the dairy co-operatives etc.

Information was collected also from various sources like, the records of Shri Hanuman Co-Operative Dudh Utpadak Sangh, Yalgud, Primary Schools and Gram Panchyat, Census Handbooks. The data collected were tabulated and presented with the help of maps and diagrams for the purpose of analysis. The analysis and interpretation was done by expository method. The study is mainly based on the case studies of selected villages presented in this study. The theoretical method is used to present development of co-operative dairy farming as the common features.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

In India co-operative dairying is an important productive activity. The co-operative dairy is an agency which carries production and sale on behalf of producers who are unable to earn good profits. In the present aspect if field study most work have been done in Geography previously, such as basis study by Dr. S. B. Sarang, namely "Dairy farming in Kolhapur District: A Geographical Analysis" (1982). There are a couple of studies in economics such as "significance of Milk co-operative in Kolhapur District by Dr. P.A. Koli (1987). Development in rural area is one of the

principal problems of engaging the attention of policy makers. Planners and administration of the country and they are trying to find the means, methods and techniques which can be applied in the rural area, without much capital cost. In this situation milk co-operative can be the best suitable instrument as they generate additional income and employment. But due to low productive capacity of animal, there is no considerable increase in milk production and per capita consumption of milk. The average per capita consumption of milk has reached up to 149 grams which is still less than the minimum requirement of 214 grams. This is because of the low production and the low productive of milk animals as compared to other countries in the world the reasons are.

“Economics of Dairy Enterprises: A case study of Weaker Section” by Mr. P.N. Gawade (1986). However there is not a single study at grass root level. So this research is going to be the first attempt of its kind of studying co-operative dairy development at the village level. Dr. Krishna Anna Chougule studied the “Co-operative Dairy farming in Warana Basin: A Study of Selected villages, (1994). Dr. Palekar Rekha Naresh, she studied the “Impact Of Milk Co-Operative on the life of rural women,: A Village in Maharashtra in December (1993).

Literacy Rate in Kolhapur District-2001-2011

The agriculture and dairy farming is the main sources of economic development of the district. Due to this overall development took place and education is not exempted. The educational facilities are found in the every tahsil of district. Especially the literacy rate was enhanced in district it is because of dairy farming. Average literacy rate of Kolhapur in 2011 were 81.51 compared to 76.93 of 2001. If things are looked out at gender wise, male and female literacy were 88.57 and 74.22 respectively. For 2001 census, same figures stood at 87.47 and 66.02 in Kolhapur District. Total literate in Kolhapur District were 2,825,845 of which male and female were 1,559,760 and 1,266,085 respectively. In 2001, Kolhapur District had 2,364,307 in its district. When the light thrown on tahsil wise literacy rate, the

highest literacy was depicted in Karvir tahsil (82.87%), it was higher than district average (76.93%) as well as state average (78.88%), and lowest in Gaganbawada tahsil i.e. 60.65 per cent. While at gender level, the male literacy rate was also noticed that the average literacy rate was 87.47 per cent and at female level it was 66.02 per cent. The absolute gap was 21.45 per cent.

Table 1
Percentage of Literacy Rate in Kolhapur District

Sr. no	Name of Tahsil	Literacy rate (2001)				Literacy rate (2011)			
		Total	Male	Female	Gender Gap in Literacy Rate	Total	Male	Female	Gender Gap in Literacy Rate
1	Shahuwadi	67.64	81.08	53.83	27.25	72.83	81.99	63.68	18.31
2	Panhala	73.78	86.21	61.36	24.85	78.94	87.15	70.73	16.42
3	Hatkanangale	79.89	89.12	70.66	18.46	84.19	89.97	78.41	11.56
4	Shirol	79.96	89.33	70.59	18.74	83.33	89.84	76.83	13.01
5	Karvir	82.87	91.04	74.71	17.33	86.50	91.51	81.50	10.01
6	Gaganbawada	60.65	75.29	46.01	29.28	69.66	80.50	58.83	21.67
7	Radhanagari	71.03	85.40	56.67	28.73	77.29	88.58	66.00	22.58
8	Kagal	63.39	65.70	61.08	04.62	78.48	87.01	69.96	17.05
9	Bhudargadh	73.01	86.14	59.89	26.25	77.70	87.84	67.57	20.27
10	Ajara	70.06	82.68	57.45	25.23	74.42	83.62	65.23	18.39
11	Gadhinglaj	72.01	83.96	60.07	23.89	76.54	85.20	68.49	16.71
12	Chandgad	67.01	80.74	53.29	27.45	73.07	82.62	63.52	19.10
	Dist. Average	76.93	87.47	66.02	21.45	81.51	88.57	74.22	14.35
	State	76.88	87.67	69.31	18.36	82.34	88.38	75.87	12.51

Source: Review of Socio- economic survey-2001&2011

Table 2
VILLAGE WISE LITERACY RATE AND MALE-FEMALE DISPARITY OF SURVEYED POPULATION, 2011

Sr. No.	Name of Village	Name of Tahsil	Name of District	Literacy Rate			Gender gap in literacy rate
				Total	Male	Female	
1	Randeviwadi	Kagal	Kolhapur	80.25	90.12	70.68	19.44
2	Mangur	Chikodi	Belgaum	65.62	75.34	55.35	18.85
3	Yalgud	Hatkanangale	Kolhapur	74.53	83.34	64.49	19.96
	Average			73.47	82.93	63.51	19.44

Source: Field Study 2010

Village wise literacy rate and male-female Disparity:

This table depicts the village wise literacy rate and male-female Disparity at case study villages. Total literacy rate of Randeviwadi, Yalgud and Mangur is 80.25%, 74.53% and 65.62% respectively. The maximum male literacy rate is 90.12% in Randeviwadi and minimum male literacy rate is 75.34% in Mangur villages. The maximum, medium and minimum literacy rate of 70.68%, 64.49% and 55.38% is in Randeviwadi, Yalgud and Mangur villages respectively. In Mangur village, gender gap in literacy rate is maximum that is 19.96%. This chart shows male-female disparity in literacy rate. The maximum literacy rate of male is 90.12 and female literacy is 70.68. The gap between two groups of male-female in literacy rate is 19.44.

The Impact on Education in the Sample Villages:

As mentioned above dairy farming is not only impacts on the economy of the people, but also on educational status of people. The government of India and Maharashtra has taken special interest in village level status in literacy. The large number of primary schools has been started in rural areas, through NGO's and

government. The Co-op Dudh Sangh also taking initiate to enhance the educational status in village by providing funds as well as other support like building, Stationeries and many other.

Table 3

EDUCATIONL ATTAINMENT OF SURVEYED VILLAGES

Sr. No.	Village Name	Primary (4 th pass)	Middle Primary (7 th pass)	Secondary (10 th pass)	H.S.C (12 th pass)	G.D	P.G.
1	Randewiwadi	10.26	23.08	33.33	15.38	12.82	5.13
2	Mangur	8.82	25	27.94	20.60	16.17	1.47
3	Yalgud	4.06	12.16	20.27	27.02	25.68	10.81
	Average	7.71	20.08	27.18	21	18.22	5.80

Source: Field Study, 2011

1) Primary Level (4th std. Pass):

The levels of educational attainment of surveyed village is quite good, due to state government policy is to cover the small villages. The average 4th standard pass children were 7.71 percent. The maximum primary level of passing was depict in the Randewiwadi, and minimum in Yalgud village (4.06%), fallows village Mangur (8.82%). The maximum student fourth standard pass because of primary school facility are available in village level in each village the primary level educational attempt is much higher than the female children.

2) Middle Primary Level (7th Std. Pass):

The proportion of middle level (7th std.) educational attainment was 20.08 per cent. The two villages viz, Mangur (25%) and Randewiwadi (23.08%) remain above average of the total attainment. The below average rate was depicts in village Yalgud i.e.12.16 per cent. This level of education was quite good with compare to the primary level of education, due to the less dropout rate in the class.

3) S.S.C Level (10th Pass):

This level of education is very importance as the turning point for the student's life where from students can change their stream of education. As far as S.S.C level of education is concern the average 10th pass rate was shown in the sample villages was very good. The average rate was 27.18 per cent 10th pass. The maximum students were completed the 10th pass class in Randeviwadi village i.e. 33.33 per cent and fallows the Mangur (27.94%) and Yalgud (20.27%).

4) H.S.C Level:

The proportion of the HSC level of education was 21 per cent in the sample villages and it was not so far good in the stream of educational development of the villages which are consider as dairy farming villages in the district. But as whole it assumes that the enrolment in this level was not up to the mark, it should take care of. Only the Yalgud village (27.02%) crossed the average rate of this level of education. The village Mangur and Randeviwadi were lagging behind.

5) Graduation and Post Graduation Level:

The graduation and post graduation level of education is considered as the sign of high development. These all three villages having a good condition in this category of education, due to the facilities of higher education is looking in the near city of Hupari which is known as silver city of the state. And also the Shivaji University, Kolhapur is one of the reasons.

The average graduation level clears was 18.22 per cent. The highest numbers of graduations were found in village Yalgud i.e. 25.68 per cent and fallows Mangur (16.17%) Randeviwadi (12.82%). The average rate of PG level was depicts only 5.80 per cent.

Conclusion:

Literacy is one of the important indices of development of in any region. Without literacy the progress is just impossible. As per the census of India 2001, a literate person is he or she who can both read and write with understanding in any language

is considered a literate person. Any literate person can protect him or her from exploitation by others. It also brings empowerment and comprehension to participate in advancing world. It helps to bring development in almost all sectors of economy including educational attainment. The average literacy of the district was observed is about 77 percent (76.93%) as per the 2001 census. As per the 2011 census, the average literacy of the district was observed is about 82 percent, (81.51%), it is increased by 4.93 per cent compared to 2001. It is inferred that the district level literacy rate was enhanced due to the agricultural as well as the supporting activity like dairy farming.

At case study villages the literacy rate was analysed and it shows positive due to the Shri Hanu, an dhadh sangh which boost the farmers for their socio-economic development and educational attainment was not excluded. Total literacy rate of Randeviwadi, Yalgud and Mangur is 80.25%, 74.53% and 65.62% respectively. The maximum male literacy rate is 90.12% in Randeviwadi and minimum male literacy rate is 75.34% in Mangur villages. The maximum, medium and minimum literacy rate of 70.68%, 64.49% and 55.38% is in Randeviwadi, Yalgud and Mangur villages respectively. In Mangur village, gender gap in literacy rate is maximum that is 19.96%. The maximum literacy rate of male is 90.12 and female literacy is 70.68. The gap between two groups of male-female in literacy rate is 19.44.

Last but not least the educational attainment was quite average level, as far as village level is concern. It concludes that, it needs to take extra attention towards the primary to SSC level of education.

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